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A Vehicle-Environment Cooperative Control Based Velocity Profile Prediction Method and Case Study in Energy Management of Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles

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ABSTRACT The vehicle-environment cooperative (VEC) control has shown a great potential to improve the vehicle performance. Consequently, it is desirable to further investigate the incorporation of VEC control. In this context, a novel method based on the VEC control is proposed to predict the velocity profile, and meanwhile the potential of the proposed method is exploited in improving the energy management performance of plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs). In particular, a specific VEC control framework is firstly introduced based on the mobile edge computation (MEC). Based on this, the compound velocity profile prediction (CVPP) method is developed, which merges the cloud server (CS), MEC servers and on-board vehicle control unit (VCU) and provides more accurate and reasonable prediction results. Finally, a case study of the proposed CVPP method is performed in the energy management of PHEVs. The results manifest that the performance of energy management strategy (EMS) is dramatically improved after providing the forecasted velocity profile information by the proposed CVPP method.

INDEX TERMS Vehicle-environment cooperative (VEC) control, mobile edge computation (MEC), velocity profile prediction, energy management, plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs)

I. INTRODUCTION

The on-going conflict among the natural resource crisis, environment pollution and economy development has arisen a serious social concern. In recent years, rapid increase of automobiles has aggravated the energy resource shortage and environment deterioration. As such, industry and academia spare no effort to explore solutions to relieve the severe issue. Vehicle-environment cooperative (VEC) control is one of ideal solutions that can improve the vehicle fuel economy and environment-friendly enhancement [1]. By means of the VEC control, the valuable information from the surrounding environment is collected and incorporated into the vehicle control, thus providing more reference information and calculation dimension for vehicle control units (VCUs) to

achieve the optimal control [2]. It is well known that the velocity profile expresses the information of driving conditions. If the future driving conditions can be known in advance, it would be quite salutary for vehicle to make the well-directed adjustment, improving the fuel economy conspicuously. As a result, how to estimate or predict the future velocity profile has become one of main research targets.

Currently, a variety of advanced methods have been proposed to predict the vehicle velocity profile, and most of them can be divided into data mining methods and mathematic calculation algorithms. Data mining methods acquire future velocity profile by statistical calculation of the shared participatory sensing data and generally describe the

future status of traffic flow according to the shared instant and historical data [3]-[5]. Due to the statistical calculation, detailed information such as local acceleration or deceleration cannot be fully provided, therefore the prediction accuracy is discounted. The widely accepted mathematic methods to predict future velocity profile are the Markov chain (MC) [6] and artificial neural network (ANN) [7]. The mathematic manners can offer detailed depiction on future driving behaviours after training by a certain amount of data to form transition probability matrixes or training matrixes. Owing to the specific calculation methods, the mathematic manners can predict future velocity profile individually, without considering the impact of traffic flow. However, the accuracy of the mathematic manners cannot be totally guaranteed in the real-time application. Actually, the data mining methods can offer the macroscopic description for future driving while the mathematic manners give the microcosmic analysis to differentiate future driving activities. The accuracy of the predicted velocity profile might be further improved if two methods were combined, referred to as a kind of VEC control.

Subject to the vehicle onboard hardware, the macroscopic and microcosmic prediction cannot be easily completed simultaneously in the VCU or other onboard control units. Recent studies in VEC control have tried to employ the cloud server (CS) to share the part workload [8]. The cloud server run control process according to the information uploaded from the vehicle and collected from roads. The control results would be sent back to the vehicle by vehicle to infrastructure communication methods [9]-[10]. With development of the 5G communication network, mobile edge computation (MEC) has drawn much attention [11], which can distribute the workload in CS to the MEC servers in the roadside base station, thereby avoiding CS overloaded, reducing data transfer time and enhancing data security and privacy. By the 5G cellular network, data collected from route segments and vehicles could be rapidly sent to MEC servers [12], some control process could be manipulated in MEC servers instead of in VCUs, thus achieving the VEC control and realizing the VCU computation intensity. Some research in terms of the electric vehicle charging planning has been performed by the MEC methods, which shows dramatic improvement [13]-[14]. The MEC based methods applied in VEC control to predict velocity profile, to the best knowledge of authors, are still quite seldom to be found in existing references.

Based on the former study, it can achieve more precise future velocity profile prediction by the VEC control on the basis of the MEC. Motivated by this, we propose a novel velocity profile prediction method based on the VEC control. The newly given method combines the macroscopic and microcosmic prediction results into the final forecasted velocity profile. The macroscopic prediction is finished in the MEC servers according to the collected information from road traffic and the control instruction from CS. The microcosmic prediction is conducted in the onboard VCU. The linear regression method incorporates the macroscopic

and microcosmic prediction results to gain the better prediction. Three innovative contributions are added in the literature:

- 1) A service-oriented VEC control framework is built which provides the infrastructure to develop the novel velocity profile prediction method. In the framework, the function of CS, MEC servers and on-board VCU is elaborated.
- 2) A compound velocity profile prediction (CVPP) method is developed that merges the macroscopic and microcosmic prediction results into the final prediction velocity profile through the cooperation of different parts in the VEC control framework. The particle filter (PF) based method contributes to the macroscopic velocity prediction and the MC based method performs the microcosmic prediction. The estimation of distribution algorithm (EDA) plays an important role in combining two prediction results.
- 3) A case study is performed to assess the performance brought by the VEC control. The predicted future velocity profiles by the CVPP method are applied to energy management strategy (EMS) in a plug-in hybrid electric vehicle (PHEV), improving the optimization effect of the EMS.

The rest of paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the newly built VEC control framework. In Section III, the CVPP method is provided with detailed description of how to achieve the predicted velocity profile. The case study about energy management in PHEV is done in Section IV, and Section V draws the main conclusion.

II. VEHICLE-ENVIRONMENT COOPERATIVE CONTROL FRAMEWORK

The designed vehicle-environment cooperative control framework, shown in Fig.1, is a publish/subscribe paradigm that is suitable for constructing the application of velocity prediction. By the efficient division-cooperation of different controllers in vehicle and environment, general driving trend and detailed individual driving behaviours can be fully considered, thus contributing to more accurate velocity profile prediction results. In this control framework, there are three types of controllers in vehicle and environment:

VCU (Vehicle Control Unit): The VCUs are the mobile control units, in which the control processes that are connected with vehicle itself are implemented. VCUs, according to the requirement from EMS, send the query to the cloud server and subscribe to the information published by the cloud server.

MEC (Mobile Edge Computation) Servers: The MEC servers, which are deployed at the roadside, share the computation burden that is originally imposed on the cloud server. In theory, each route segment should be assigned at least one MEC server, and the status of the route segment, like macroscopic traffic velocity, could be estimated in the MEC servers. Therefore, a large amount of computational resource in cloud server could be released for the core task.

FIGURE 1. The vehicle-environment cooperative control framework.

FIGURE 2. The illustration of the CVPP method.

Cloud Server: The centralized control unit releases the calculation order to MEC servers according to the query from VCU. Meanwhile, the cloud server splices the estimation results from several MEC servers and publishes the results calculated by the MEC servers.

The communication among the cloud server, MEC servers and VCUs are realized by the 5G communication, the communication speed and bandwidth of which could

guarantee the real-time application demand. In the VEC control, the microcosmic velocity profile is predicted in the VCU based on individual driving behaviours. Macroscopic velocity profile, which is on behalf of the general driving trend of vehicles on a given route, is completed by several MEC servers after receiving the order from the cloud server (Edge calculation broadcasting in Fig. 1). Each MEC server is in charge of estimating the macroscopic performance of vehicles on certain route segment and uploads the estimation results to the cloud server (Edge calculation publication in Fig. 1). In

MEC servers, shared instantaneous data by vehicles on the route segment is statistically analyzed (real-time data monitoring and collection). The estimated macroscopic velocity profile segments are spliced in the cloud server and then sent back to VCU (Macroscopic prediction publication in Fig. 1). Finally, the forecasted macroscopic and microcosmic vehicle profiles are incorporated into the final predicted velocity profile in the VCU.

III. COMPOUND VELOCITY PROFILE PREDICTION METHOD

The illustration of the CVPP method is depicted in Fig. 2. In the CVPP method, the macroscopic velocity profile is predicted by a two-stage work that includes the status estimation by PF in the MEC servers. In VCU, the microcosmic velocity profile is forecasted by the MC based method. The predicted macroscopic and microcosmic velocity profile are synthesized by a linear regression method. The parameters in the linear regression are obtained by the EDA offline. In the following sections, details of velocity profile prediction are described.

A. Macroscopic velocity prediction in MEC servers

The macroscopic velocity offers the general depiction of the future driving trend on the route, reflecting the influence on vehicle driving from the environment. To obtain the macroscopic velocity profile, a two-stage work should be conducted including traffic status estimation and velocity prediction. The traffic status estimation, as the key step that determines the prediction accuracy, is still a tricky problem due to the complex and high nonlinear characteristics of the traffic, corrupted data by sensors malfunction and noise. To realize nicety traffic state estimation, the PF, benefiting from the Bayesian and Monte Carlo theory, is implemented [15].

1) THE PRINCIPLE OF PF

As is discussed in the Bayesian theory, the posterior probability distribution can be employed to estimate and fix revision of the prior probability distribution [16]. As such, the posterior probability distribution could be quite valuable in status estimation. The calculation of the posterior probability distribution can be formulated as:

$$(x_k | z_{1:k}) = \frac{p(z_k | x_k) p(x_k | z_{1:k-1})}{p(z_k | z_{1:k-1})} \quad (1)$$

where x_k and z_k is the system state and corresponded measurement, respectively. A state estimation problem can be written as:

$$\begin{cases} x_k = f(x_{k-1}, w_{k-1}) \\ z_k = h(x_k, n_k) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where w_k and n_k is the noise existing in state and measurement, respectively. In the PF, a set of sample points and their weights extracted by Monte Carlo method approximate the posterior probability distribution [17]. Each sample point and its weight ($x_{0:k}^i, \omega_k^i$) is called the particle. The posterior probability density can be approximated as:

$$p(x_{0:k} | z_{1:k}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \omega_k^i \delta(x_{0:k} - x_{0:k}^i) \quad (3)$$

By assuming that $\{x_{0:k}^i\}_{i=1}^N$ can be acquired by importance density $q(x_{0:k} | z_{1:k})$, the particle weight can be expressed as:

$$\omega_k^i \propto \frac{p(x_{0:k} | z_{1:k})}{q(x_{0:k} | z_{1:k})} \quad (4)$$

The particle weight can be chosen by importance sampling, and the importance density of each particle is assumed to be calculated by:

$$q(x_{0:k} | z_{1:k}) = q(x_k | x_{0:k-1}, z_{1:k}) q(x_{0:k-1} | z_{1:k-1}) \quad (5)$$

Hence, the particle weight can be written as:

$$\omega_k^i \propto \frac{p(z_k | x_k^i) p(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i) p(x_{0:k-1}^i | z_{1:k-1})}{q(x_k^i | x_{0:k-1}^i, z_{1:k}) q(x_{0:k-1}^i | z_{1:k-1})} = \omega_{k-1}^i \frac{p(z_k | x_k^i) p(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i)}{q(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i, z_k)} \quad (6)$$

Supposing $q(x_k | x_{0:k-1}, z_{1:k}) = q(x_k | x_{k-1}, z_k)$, the importance density is only connected with x_{k-1} and z_k . Therefore, the particle weight can be determined,

$$\omega_k^i \propto \omega_{k-1}^i \frac{p(z_k | x_k^i) p(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i)}{q(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i, z_k)} \quad (7)$$

It is widely accepted that (8) can be applied to calculate the importance density.

$$q(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i, z_k) = p(x_k^i | x_{k-1}^i) \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the particle weight can be rewritten as:

$$\omega_k^i \propto \omega_{k-1}^i p(z_k | x_k^i) \quad (9)$$

Finally, by normalizing the particle weight, and the posterior probability distribution can be attained,

$$p(x_k | z_{1:k}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^N \tilde{\omega}_k^i \delta(x_k - x_k^i) \quad (10)$$

where $\tilde{\omega}_k^i$ is the normalized weigh.

2) MACROSCOPIC VELOCITY PREDICTION BY PF

The macroscopic velocity prediction is a two-stage work, i.e., the traffic state estimation and the future velocity prediction. To estimate the traffic state on the given route segment, following equations are employed:

$$\begin{cases} v_{s,\theta}(k+1) = v_{s,\theta}(k) + \frac{T}{\tau} \left(V(\rho_{s,\theta}(k)) - v_{s,\theta}(k) \right) \\ \quad + \frac{T}{L_s} v_{s,\theta}(k) (v_{s,\theta-1}(k) - v_{s,\theta}(k)) \\ \quad - \frac{\eta T}{\tau L_s} \frac{\rho_{s,\theta+1}(k) - \rho_{s,\theta}(k)}{\rho_{s,\theta}(k) + \psi} + \xi_{s,\theta}^v(k) \\ \quad z_{s,\theta}^v(k) = v_{s,\theta} + n_{s,\theta}^v(k) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $q_{s,\theta}$, $\rho_{s,\theta}$ and $v_{s,\theta}$ are the flow, density and average speed of the θ th segment, respectively; T denotes the time interval; $\xi_{s,\theta}^v$ is the random variable which represents the stochastic characteristic in velocity dynamic; $v_{free,s}$ means the free flow velocity of the route segment; $\rho_{crit,s}$ expresses the critical density; and $n_{s,\theta}^v$ is the measurement noise. In addition, τ , η , a_s , and ψ are the model filtering parameters. After obtaining accurate estimation on traffic status, equation (12) can be used to predict future velocity:

$$v_{s,\theta}(k+n) = v_{s,\theta}(k)(1+\varphi)^n + \chi_{s,\theta}^v(k) \quad (12)$$

where $\chi_{s,\theta}^v(k)$ is stochastic value.

B. Microcosmic velocity prediction in on-board VCU

The microcosmic velocity, actually, is the individual delineation of vehicle future behaviours according to current status. MC has been widely accepted as a reasonable method to model driver behaviours for its satisfactory performance in characterizing the stochastic process. When implementing the MC in describing the random process, the probability distribution of the next state is only determined by the current state and not related with the previous states[18]. In the MC, the transition matrix P depicts the Markov process. In P , the probability that the current state x_i at time n switches to next state x_j at time $n + 1$ can be expressed as:

$$p_{ij} = P_r(x(n + 1) = x_j | x(n) = x_i) \quad (13)$$

In (13), the transition probability can be calculated as

$$p_{ij} = \frac{N_{ij}}{\sum_j N_{ij}} \quad (14)$$

where N_{ij} is the number of transition times switching from one state to another.

When taking advantage of MC to predict velocity, the vehicle speed and acceleration are dispersed to describe the stochastic vehicle driving condition. In the transition probability matrix, the velocity v and acceleration a are indexed by i and j in row and line, respectively. Thus, the MC can be alternatively expressed as:

$$p_{ij} = P_r(a(n + 1) = a_j | v(n) = v_i) \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) models the one-step Markov process. To increase the prediction accuracy, the one-step Markov process is extended to the multi-step Markov process by following the transition probability matrix, as

$$P_r(a(n) = a_j | v(n - 1) = v_{i1}, \dots, v(n - s) = v_{is}) \quad (16)$$

where s is the step number of the multi-step MC process. The procedure of velocity prediction by the multi-step MC can be described as:

- 1) Discretize the velocity and acceleration into finite values based on the given driving data.
- 2) Calculate the transition probabilities for the next n steps based on (16). In particular, at each step, the acceleration of next n steps is logged given the current velocity and acceleration. Then the status transitions from current velocity is recorded and the probability is calculated.
- 3) Build the transition probability matrix $P_{n,1-step}, P_{n,2-step}, \dots, P_{n,s-step}$ for each discretized velocity.
- 4) Predict acceleration of each step based on the specific transition probability matrix.
- 5) Obtain the velocity profile within the stated horizon based on current velocity and acceleration for the next few steps.

C. Synthetization to the final predicted velocity profile in on-board VCU

After acquiring the macroscopic and microcosmic velocity profile, two differentiated velocity profiles are combined into the final predicted velocity profile by the following equation:

$$v_{p_hori}(i) = av_{macr_hori}(i) + bv_{micr_hori}(i) \quad (17)$$

where v_{p_hori} , v_{macr_hori} and v_{micr_hori} are the final, macroscopic and microcosmic velocity profile, respectively; i is the i th velocity point in the prediction horizon; a and b are the degree of the contribution (DOC) of the macroscopic and microcosmic velocity.

FIGURE 3. The transition probability matrixes with different prediction length: 5 seconds (above) and 20 seconds (below).

In previous research, it has been proved that the prediction horizon can determine the accuracy to large extent. Fig. 3 illustrates the transition probability matrixes with different prediction lengths in MC. Apparently, transition states in the transition probability matrixes become more disperse with increase of the prediction horizon, thereby making prediction accuracy worse. After fully investigating the correlation feature, prediction error and calculation burden of the MC and PF based method, the prediction length is set to 10 s.

The DOC parameters in (17) are estimated by the EDA, which is one of evolution algorithms that has been proved to hold fantastic performance in parameter optimization and other optimal control problems [19]. The EDA searches the global optimal solution in each iteration by evaluating the total performance of the population based on the probabilistic model [20]. On the contrary, GA and PSO try to find the optimal solutions by focusing on individual performance through individual variation and combination [21]. In other words, the EDA provides the optimal solutions through the macroscopic evaluation while the GA and PSO accomplish the optimal control by the microcosmic analysis. The execution

process of the EDA is shown in Fig. 4 and the pseudocode of the EDA is provided in Table I. The seeding method, sampling method, replacement method, selection

FIGURE 4. The illustration on the process of the EDA method, learning method and probabilistic model referred in Table I are listed in Table II.

To accelerate the calculation process of the EDA, some calculation is made to choose the most appropriate iteration and population number. In Fig. 5, n_{pop} is the number of population and n_{iter} denotes the number of iteration. As shown in Fig. 5, the accuracy of parameter estimation decreases with increase of the population and iteration scale. Meanwhile, the computation time also increases with the larger scale of population and iteration. Comprehensively considering the balance between accuracy and computation burden, the number of iteration and population are set to 450 and 15, respectively.

TABLE I
PSEUDOCODE OF THE EDA

1	Initializing
2	Setting the population size, number of variables, constraints, terminal conditions, probabilistic model
3	Do {
4	If t=0
5	Generating the initial population E_0 by the seeding method
6	Evaluating the population by the fitness function
7	Else
8	Sampling a E_{sample} population by the sampling method
9	Evaluating the new population E_{sample} by the fitness function
10	Generating the E_t population from E_{t-1} , E_{sample} , E_t^s by the replacement method
11	Selecting a set of points from E_t^s by the selection method
12	Computing the probabilistic model of E_t^s by the learning method
13	t=t+1
14	} Until the terminal condition is met

TABLE II
METHOD APPLIED IN EDA

Seeding method	Sampling population from the uniform distribution
Sampling method	Univariate Gaussian model [22]
Replacement method	Combining the selected individuals with the sampled individuals
Selection method	Letting the selection probability of each individual be proportional to its fitness
Learning method	Greedy score [23]
Probabilistic model	Gaussian network [24]

FIGURE 5. The estimation error and computation time.

IV. CASE STUDY: INVESTIGATION PERFORMANCE OF THE CVPP METHOD IN ENERGY MANAGEMENT IMPROVEMENT IN PHEV

A. Energy management strategy in PHEV

EMS has been proved to be the core factor in exploring the fuel economy potential of PHEVs. In past research, a variety of energy management methods such as model predictive control (MPC) [25], dynamic programming (DP) [26] have been fully investigated. In some optimal methods, lacking the precise pre-knowledge of the future driving conditions may lead to deterioration of the management effect [27]. From this point of view, one of the core steps to improve the controlling effect of EMS is to acquire the precise velocity profile. Similarly, it should be also feasible to evaluate the proposed CVPP method from the perspective of control effect of the EMS.

The case study about the effect optimization of the EMS is performed on a parallel PHEV, of which the configuration is shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen, the internal combustion engine (ICE) and electric motor are connected through a single axle. The clutch and generator are in charge of the ICE operation and switch of the operation mode. Torques from the ICE and electric motor are transmitted to wheels through a 6-

speed automatic gearbox. The detailed parameters of the powertrain are listed in Table III.

FIGURE 6. The configuration of the parallel PHEV.

The dynamic function of the vehicle powertrain can be expressed as:

$$T_{wheel} = (mgf\cos\alpha + mgsina + \frac{1}{2}C_DAv^2 + \xi \frac{dv}{dt})r_{wheel} \quad (18)$$

where T_{wheel} is the torque acted on the wheel; m , g , and α denote the vehicle mass, gravity acceleration, and gradient, respectively; C_D , A , and v state the aerodynamic drag coefficient, vehicle frontal area, and vehicle speed, respectively; f is the rolling resistance factor, ξ is the correction coefficient of rotatingmass; and r_{wheel} is the wheel radius.

To evaluate the engine performance in energy consumption, a benchmarking test based static model is preferred. The static model shows relationship of engine net efficiency and engine torque by following equation:

$$\eta_{eng}(T_{eng}, n_{eng}) = \frac{T_{eng}n_{eng}}{Q_{lhv}\dot{m}_f} \quad (19)$$

where T_{eng} is the engine torque, η_{eng} is the engine net efficiency, n_{eng} is the engine rotating speed, Q_{lhv} is the fuel lower heating value, and \dot{m}_f is the fuel consumption rate.

Electric motor in the parallel PEHV is the permanent magnet synchronous motor. Dynamic of electric motor is neglected in this paper. Electric motor, as is described, can operate as tractive motor and generator, the relationship of torque and power can be expressed by (20).

$$P_{em} = \begin{cases} \frac{T_{em}\omega_{em}}{\eta_{mot}} T_{em} > 0 \\ T_{em}\omega_{em}\eta_{gen} T_{em} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

where P_{em} , ω_{em} , T_{em} are the motor power, speed and torque, respectively; η_{mot} and η_{gen} are the efficiency of electric motor in tractive mode and generator mode, respectively.

A simple equivalent circuit model that characterizes the battery electrical performance and neglects the effect of temperature and ageing, is adopted to model the battery. Based on it, the battery state of charge (SOC) can be calculated,

$$SOC = -\frac{V_{oc} - \sqrt{V_{oc}^2 - 4R_{int}P_{batt}}}{2R_{int}Q_{batt}} \quad (21)$$

where V_{oc} means open circuit voltage of battery, R_{int} denotes the internal resistance of battery, and Q_{batt} represents the battery capacity.

TABLE III
COMPONENT PAPRMETERS IN THE PARALLEL PHEV

		Displacement	2.0 [L]
Engine	Maximum Power	103 [kW] @6200 [rpm]	
	Maximum Torque	160 [Nm] @2500~6000 [rpm]	
	Maximum Speed	124 [kW]	
Motor	Maximum Torque	305 [Nm]	
	Maximum Speed	12480 [rpm]	
	Type	Lithium-ion	
Battery	Capacity	21 [Ah]	
	Nominal Voltage	300 [V]	
	Maximum Power	8.5 [kW]	
Generator (Starter)	Maximum Torque	45 [Nm]	
	Type	6-Speed AT	

The MPC based EMS is chosen in the case study. In most application of the MPC based method, DP is regarded as the solver algorithm [28]. To implement the MPC, DP searches every possible optimal solution in the predicted horizon, thus forming the optimal decision sequence [28]. The first solution in the optimal decision sequence is applied for the current time step. In the second step, DP is implemented to generate the new optimal sequence to find the solution for the second step in the updated prediction horizon. In the case study, the battery SOC is the state variable and power distribution ratio between the ICE and battery is considered as the control variable. The cost function can be formulated as:

$$J_k = \int_{t_k}^{t_k+H_p} (\dot{m}_f(u(t)))^2 \quad (22)$$

where H_p is the length of the predicted horizon, t_k is the current time step, and \dot{m}_f is the instant fuel consumption. The constraints in terms of the optimal control problem can be summarized as,

$$\begin{cases} SOC_{min} \leq SOC \leq SOC_{max} \\ P_{batt_min} \leq P_{batt} \leq P_{batt_max} \\ T_{mot_min} \leq T_{mot} \leq T_{mot_max} \\ T_{eng_min} \leq T_{eng} \leq T_{eng_max} \\ \omega_{mot_min} \leq \omega_{mot} \leq \omega_{mot_max} \\ \omega_{eng_min} \leq \omega_{eng} \leq \omega_{eng_max} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

where P_{batt} , T_{mot} , T_{eng} , ω_{mot} and ω_{eng} are the battery power, motor torque, engine torque, motor speed, and engine speed, respectively; subscripts min and max denote the minimum and maximum value of each variable, respectively. In the case study, the prediction horizon length is 10 s, the sampling time is 1 s, and the discrete intervals of battery SOC in each time step is 0.005.

B. Case study

1) EVALUATION ON VELOCITY PROFILE PREDICTION ACCURACY IN REAL-TIME APPLICATION

To evaluate the accuracy of the proposed CVPP method and the performance in the real-time application, a comparative study is performed. We run the simulation test on a workstation with an Intel Xeon-E31270 @ 3.4 GHz, and the step computation for each MPC based EMS is 0.47 s. Two driving cycles are implemented in the comparative test, and the real velocity profiles of the two driving cycles are shown in Fig. 7. In addition to the CVPP method, the prediction accuracy and computation time of the ANN, MC and participatory sensing data (PSD) based method are also calculated. In the case study, the root mean square error (RMSE) is employed to evaluate the prediction accuracy. For the ANN based method, we choose the radial basis function NNs (RBF-NNs) with a different number of hidden layer nodes according to [29]. For the MC based method, we choose the one step and five step MC, respectively based on the study from [29]. For the PSD based method and the macroscopic velocity prediction, the data come from the database shared by Microsoft [30]. Table IV lists the results of the comparison study.

TABLE IV
COMPARE RESULTS OF RMSE AND COMPUTATION TIME

Driving Route	Prediction Method	RMSE	Computation Time (s)
1	CVPP	1.8755	0.418
	RBF-NN (50)	2.2312	0.297
	RBF-NN (100)	2.2017	0.311
	One step MC	2.9743	1.395
	Five step MC	2.9544	1.463
	PSD	4.7965	0.271
2	CVPP	1.8643	0.419
	RBF-NN (50)	2.2116	0.305
	RBF-NN (100)	2.1931	0.310
	One step MC	2.8755	1.384
	Five step MC	2.8649	1.459
	PSD	4.7122	0.266

As listed in Table IV, the RMSE of the CVPP method are lower than other methods. The MC and PSD based algorithms cannot provide more precise prediction results, since they describe the future driving conditions only based on the incomprehensive information rather than full investigation of the macroscopic and microcosmic driving behaviours of the vehicle. The CVPP method, which fully take advantage over the 5-step MC and PSD, provides more reasonable description of future driving. Although the computation time of RBF-NNs is smaller than that of the CVPP method, more accurate prediction results neutralize the drawback. In the simulation, the total computation time, which includes the prediction calculation and MPC calculation, is smaller than 1 s, guaranteeing the predicting effect in real time application.

2) EVALUATION OF MPC BASED EMS OPTIMIZATION

As discussed above, the performance of the MPC based control is influenced by the horizon prediction accuracy significantly, which provides a suitable platform to investigate the effect of the CVPP method further. Fig. 8 illustrates the

battery SOC trajectories by different EMSs on two different routes (shown in Fig. 7). To be specific, the battery SOC trajectories by the MPC based methods are closer to that by DP than by the CD-CS method. The battery SOC trajectories by the MPC based methods and DP decrease gradually and evenly in both CD and CS stages, meaning more balanced engine and battery power output. The phenomenon results from the DP and MPC based method can search the possible global optimal solutions in the given or predicted horizon, while the CD-CS strategy controls engine start only based on current status. Among the MPC based methods, horizon prediction accuracy prompts the general performance. With the less precisely predicted velocity profile, the battery SOC would decrease fast. As a result, more fuel might be consumed.

TABLE V
FUEL CONSUMPTION BY DIFFERENT EMSs

Driving Cycle	Operation Stage	EMS	Fuel Consumption (g)	Normalized Average (%)
Cycle 1	CD	DP	498.12	100
		MPC with CVPP	518.60	96.05
		MPC with ANN	524.83	94.91
		MPC with MC	532.52	93.54
		MPC with PSD	541.37	92.01
		CD-CS	560.82	88.82
Cycle 1	CS	DP	519.67	100
		MPC with CVPP	542.45	95.80
		MPC with ANN	549.33	94.60
		MPC with MC	558.18	93.11
		MPC with PSD	564.25	92.09
		CD-CS	579.34	89.72
Cycle 2	CD	DP	265.17	100
		MPC with CVPP	277.84	95.44
		MPC with ANN	281.49	94.22
		MPC with MC	284.85	93.09
		MPC with PSD	287.89	92.11
		CD-CS	298.04	88.97
Cycle 2	CS	DP	276.45	100
		MPC with CVPP	289.68	95.43
		MPC with ANN	291.12	94.96
		MPC with MC	296.62	93.21
		MPC with PSD	300.42	92.02
		CD-CS	309.33	89.37

Table V lists the fuel consumption of different EMSs on different driving cycles in both CD and CS stages. In the case study, the total fuel consumption is calculated by converting the electricity consumption into equivalent fuel consumption. According to the results listed in Table V, the MPC based method with CVPP achieves better fuel economy compared

with other MPC based methods. Considering the evaluation results in the former section, it can be concluded that more accurate velocity prediction contributes to the EMS performance improvement. For the CD-CS strategy, the fuel consumption in the CD or CS stage is not optimal. Even though electric energy is more favoured in the CD stage, the poor efficiencies of the electric path under some conditions make the equivalent fuel consumption larger.

V. Conclusion

In this paper, a method to predict future velocity profile based on the VEC control is proposed. The CVPP method takes advantage over the cooperative work among cloud server, MEC sever and on-board VCU, and generates more accurate velocity profile based on the detailed information from vehicle and environment. The case study reveals that the accuracy of the raised method is higher than the existed MC, ANN, PSD

FIGURE 7. Velocity profiles of the two driving cycles for case study.

FIGURE 8. Battery SOC trajectories by different EMSs.

based method and holds the rational performance in the real-time implementation.

In the future study, we would focus on the real test of the CVPP method based on the multi-source hardware-in-the-loop platform. In addition, the CVPP method would be implemented in other VEC problems such as electric vehicle charging management and autonomous velocity optimization.

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